

DESIGNING AND VALIDATING TEACHERS' SOCIAL CAPITAL SCALE (TSCS)

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Abstract:

Social capital is a positive product of human behaviour facilitating cooperation and mutually supporting relations in communities. Research studies have confirmed the influence of social capital on social, educational, political, moral, spiritual and psychological problems among the learners and teachers at different stages. This motivated the author to prepare and validate "Teachers' Social Capital Scale" with the objective of measuring teachers' social capital. Social capital is perceived on three dimensions: structural, cognitive and relational. The tool, developed by the author, consists of 24 statements in a 5 point Likert scale. Validity of the tool has been established with the grade norm on a sample of 1,250 school teachers, representing the eastern, western, northern, southern and central regions of Tamil Nadu. The obtained co-efficient of Cronbach's Alpha 0.84, predicts the high level of internal consistency of the tool. Scoring procedure and norms for interpretation is discussed in detail to ensure proper application of the tool.

Key Words: Social Capital, Structure, Cognitive, Relational, Bonding, Bridging, Linking.

Introduction:

Lyda Judson Hanifan (1916) was the first person to employ the related concept of social capital for a ground-breaking act of securing local support for effective supervision of rural schools and their overall developments, through assured "social cohesion and personal investments from the community". According to him, 'social capital' does not mean real estate or personal property, cold cash; rather it stands for those characteristics in life which tend to offer those 'tangible substances' of a group of individuals and families, forming a social unit of good will, fellowship, mutual sympathy, and social intercourse. Moreover, when an individual of a group happens to contact with the neighbour and that person interacts with another neighbour, there occurs accumulation of social capital which satisfies the individual's social needs and that of the whole community. It is observed from the studies conducted in the area of social dynamics, sociability, social-emotional functioning, social groups, etc; the factor 'social capital' has been invariably treated as an inherent variable of the trait or the condition in question. But, the research reports published in those areas from the region of Tamil Nadu reveal that the researchers have not considered the concept 'social capital' worth focusing on the problems conceived by them. The non-availability of a properly validated data collecting instrument for assessing social capital may be a reason for such phenomenal omission of social capital. Hence, the author has designed and validated, Teachers' Social Capital Scale.

Concept - Social Capital:

The concept, 'social capital' is unthinkable in the absence of a human assembly, generally marked as a social group prevailing in a geographical area guiding and guarding the members of the group from other social groups impeding, interfering or damaging the life, as well as the life style of its members. Besides, the unseen protection offered by the social group to their members from the negative or not conducive characteristics of the other groups, they indirectly induce their members to avail the positive qualities and development oriented innovations or strategies found in other groups for the good of their own people. As a larger society in a conglomeration of several social groups with each one having its own smaller or sub-units, the transaction of knowledge, skills, values, etc would be going on silently and continually among them to get reflected at the social level.

In this context, social capital is defined as, "the effective functioning of social groups through interpersonal relationships and a shared understanding encompassing a shared sense of identity, shared norms, shared values, trust, cooperation and reciprocity. Thus, it comes to mean that "social capital is a measure of the value of resources, which are tangible (property, liquid cash, interests earned, etc) and intangible ones (trust, norms, values, reciprocation, etc.) and the impact that these relationships have on the resources involved in each relationship and on the larger groups". As such social capital is helpful to explain the factors causing enhancement in the performance of different social groups, superior administrative and managerial practices, growth and development of entrepreneurial concerns, values accrued from strategic associations, and appearance of newly formed communities (Wikipedia).

Will Kenton (2019) observes that social capital is a positive product of human interaction. That is, it may include useful information, innovative ideas, and future opportunities. In the context of industrial/business organizations, their success is largely attributed to personal relationships and networks both within and outside the organizations.

Rationale:

Thomas Sander (2015) observes that social capital is “the collective value of social networks and inclinations that arise from these networks to do things for each other”. He further interprets that social capital provides specific benefits that flow from the trust, reciprocity, information and cooperation associated with social networks, which creates value for the people who are connected and for bystanders.

Robert D. Putnam suggests that social capital would facilitate cooperation and mutually supportive relations in communities and nations and would therefore be a valuable means of combating many of the social disorders inherent in modern societies (as cited in Stam et al., 2014). While Putnam considers social capital as a resource helpful for public good or for the benefit of individuals, Pierre Bourdieu uses this concept to show the possibility of starting a mechanism for generating reproduction of inequality. According to him, the wealthy and powerful are likely to exploit their “old boys’ networks” as well as other social capital to their benefit, to their social class and their family (as cited in Alejandro, 1998). However, James Coleman’s conception of social capital is based on the perception that it is a neutral resource that facilitates any manner of action that may elevate the society a better one or pull down its status (as cited in Foley & Edwards, 1997). Nan Lin (2001) conceived social capital as individualistic approach for the reason it relies on “investment in social relations with expected returns in the market place.” Robinson, Schmid and Siles (2002) argued that social capital needs to be defined as sympathy. According to them, the object of another’s sympathy will have social capital and those who sympathize for others will provide social capital.

In order to expand the scope of social capital, Daniel P. Aldrich (2012) has put forth three mechanisms of the concept as: bonding social capital, bridging social capital, and linking social capital. Bonding social capital occurs by the relationship an individual will have with family members, friends, peers, neighbours and such of those closer to him, to his family, to his place of residence and working or learning with him. It provides the strong and the most sustaining form of social capital. Bridging social capital is caused by the extended relationship one may have beyond the inner circle of associates, that is, friends of friends, families closely tied up with family of his own, playmates attached with one’s own playmates, people from outside associated with his neighbours, etc. This sort of extended social capital, formed of bridging the relationships already formed by the individuals with the outer circles of similar social groups, serves as the secondary strength to the already secured bonding capital. Linking social capital is the one formed of relationship secured with members of distant social groups by an actor of a particular group. That is, a union is developed with members of an altogether strange group of diverse nature. This sort of social capital enables the members to leverage a far wider range of resources than that are available in the community (Woolcock, 2001). Bourdieu gives an illustration of a business man having membership in golf clubs will secure a wider network which provides exclusive openings for him for further developments (as cited in Wynne, 1999; Field, 2003).

While analyzing the role of social capital to find how it may lead to the formation of intellectual capital, Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998) were led to conclude that social capital should be approached in respect of three clusters - structural, relational and cognitive. The structural dimension of social capital is said to be related to individual ability, making weak and strong ties with others within the system. The relational dimension focused on the nature of connection between individuals. It is well manifested through trust of others, as well as cooperation and identification they have within the networks. The cognitive dimension has its focus on shared meaning, representations and interpretations, the individuals or groups will have with one another.

In addition to this understanding of three dimensional structure of social capital put forth by Nahapiet and Ghoshal, the author reviewed one highly significant and relevant analytical paper on ‘Dimensions of Social Capital – Structural, Cognitive and Relational’ written by Tristan Claridge (2018) to make out a clear conclusion about the nature of social capital. The theoretical estimate of Tristan Claridge about the constructs of social capital may be presented in three parts as stated below:

- Firstly, in the beginning, the researchers had the view that social capital is constituted by only two dimensions, that is, predominantly by structural and cognitive dimensions (Krishna & Uphoff, 1999; van Bastelaer, 2001; Grootaert et al., 2003). Beyond 2004 only, reference to three dimensions has been widely used and accepted as a framework (Andrews, 2010; Sally & Urs, 2011; Ansari et al., 2012; Al-Tabbaa & Samuel, 2016).
- Secondly, it is improbable to consider that one dimension of social capital can exist without the presence of the other two forms, revealing the nature of interconnectedness of all the three dimensions.
- Thirdly, it is noted that some of the researchers seem to rely on one or more dimensions necessitated by the level or width of the investigations. Researchers interested in social capital at the individual level are likely to concentrate more on the structural dimensions. However, when the researchers are attracted towards controlling their investment in their social relationships but fail to do so accurately, they may rely on other dimensions, as social capital is interconnected by all.

Thus, Tristan Claridge has shown that social capital is formed of all the three factors - structural, cognitive and relational - differing in quality and nature but tied up together strongly by their interconnectedness. It is reported that all the three dimensions of social capital are directly exclusive and at the

same time they are strongly inclusive of the factor social capital. Hence, the author chose to make use of the three dimensional aspect of social capital created by Nahapiet and Ghoshal (1998) and factually exposed by Tristan Claridge as a valid framework for understanding social capital of people of different occupations including teachers. It is known from all these, that one can understand social capital by the level of interconnectedness, quality and nature of these connections, and extent of common shared visions (Akram et al., 2016).

On the basis of this, the proposed tool will be helpful to assess the overall social capital of the teachers of different cadres as well as in terms of the dimensions – *Structural* (connection among actors), *Relational* (trust between actors), and *Cognitive* (shared goals and values among actors). The following table provides the characteristic features of the dimensions of social capital:

Structural	Structural	Relational
Social structure	Shared understandings	Nature and quality of relationships
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network ties and configuration • Roles, rules, precedents, and procedures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shared language, codes and narratives • Shared values, attitudes and believes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trust and trustworthiness • Norms and sanctions • Obligations and expectations • Identity and identification

Tristan Claridge (2018)

Preparation of Test Items:

After fixing the three dimensions and their corresponding sub-units, the author generated the test items as given below:

Dimension I: Social Structure (Structural)

S.No	Statements
1	I have close ties with teachers of different departments of our institution.
2	I am familiar with teachers of other institutions in our locality.
3	I am a member of an academic oriented/social community related organization.
4	I take part in subject oriented associations functioning in different institutions.
5	I hold membership in certain interest clubs.
6	I am aware of different roles a teacher has to play inside and outside of the class.
7	My past students are in good positions in the society.
8	I strictly follow the school procedure in executing my planned activities.
9	I am an active member of the local health/fitness club.
10	I feel, I am regarded in the local community as an expert in education.

Dimension II: Shared Understandings (Cognitive)

S.No	Statements
1	I know the implications of the code of conduct of teachers.
2	I am careful about my language while interacting with my students.
3	My directions to students are short, progressive and to the point.
4	While narrating, I restrict myself to avoid unrelated and lengthy explanations.
5	I put up good teacher behaviour before my students.
6	I am conscious of the problems arising in the class due to the negative attitudes of a few.
7	I appreciate the beliefs of my students; however, I let them understand what my beliefs are.
8	I believe in the goodness of pleasing words and expressions to calm down the turbulent hearts of students.
9	I uphold the moral values as the primary ones in the life of students.
10	My classroom instructions help students understand their importance, relevance and application to real life.

Dimension III: Nature and Quality of Relationships (Relational)

S.No	Statements
1	I trust the goodness of my students to reciprocate my sincerity.
2	I am a person of worth to all those who are in contact with me.
3	The parents of my students acknowledge my trustworthiness.
4	My students are capable of differentiating their friends of true trustworthiness from the fake ones.
5	I introduce my students to emulate the spirit of living for others.
6	My students are hesitant to mock at others as it degrades their dignity.
7	My students don't exhibit any odd or affected behaviour.
8	I make it a point to make at least one past student to interact with the students of my class.
9	I help the students of my class to develop certain unique characteristics that differentiate them from others.

10	I am happy that my students have started practicing their obligation to family, school and to the community.
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On the whole, the researcher has prepared 30 test items which are to be included in the draft tool. Each item is to be answered by the respondents in a five point scale as ‘Strongly Agree’, ‘Agree’, ‘Undecided’, ‘Disagree’, and ‘Strongly Disagree’. The consolidated number of statements under each dimension is provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Number of Items per Category of the Teachers’ Social Capital Scale

S.No	Dimensions	No. of Statements
1	Social Structure	10
2	Shared Understandings	10
3	Nature and Quality of Relationships	10
Total		30

Pilot Study I:

A pilot study was undertaken as stated below for validating the tool being constructed.

Content Validity:

Copies of the draft tool were provided to two other experts guiding doctoral studies in education in different universities, and a retired professor of education with a request to study the appropriateness of the statements prepared and offer their suggestions for better alterations or modifications. The suggestions given by the experts to modify the structure of statements have been executed. Thus the content validity of the Teachers’ Social Capital Scale has been established.

Item Validity:

To establish the item validity, the modified draft tool was administered to 100 teachers of different cadres working in government, government aided, and private schools in and around Chennai, Tamil Nadu. Using the data collected from the sample respondents, the validity of each item has been established by subjecting the data to Goodness of Fit Test, which is otherwise called Chi-square one sample test. It is one of the several applications of Chi-square test (Louis Cohen, 1976). Here it is used to test the null hypothesis formed for every statement in the draft tool that “the responses obtained under Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree are not by choice.”

Table 2: Goodness of Fit value for Items of the Teachers’ Social Capital Scale

S.No	Chi Square Value	Remark on H ₀	S.No	Chi Square Value	Remark on H ₀
1	21.59	Rejected	16	30.48	Rejected
2	24.51	Rejected	17	27.16	Rejected
3	30.56	Rejected	18	34.29	Rejected
4	28.49	Rejected	19	33.51	Rejected
5	6.7*	Accepted	20	6.1*	Accepted
6	26.48	Rejected	21	28.46	Rejected
7	22.15	Rejected	22	22.41	Rejected
8	29.48	Rejected	23	27.48	Rejected
9	27.84	Rejected	24	7.2*	Accepted
10	29.26	Rejected	25	18.26	Rejected
11	23.16	Rejected	26	33.56	Rejected
12	19.50	Rejected	27	31.48	Rejected
13	28.46	Rejected	28	18.29	Rejected
14	29.72	Rejected	29	29.45	Rejected
15	5.4*	Accepted	30	26.53	Rejected

Note: 9.49 significant at 5% level & 13.28 significant at 1% level

* Item deleted

The above table indicates the Goodness of Fit value for each of the 30 items and also the details about acceptance or rejection of the stated null hypothesis with regard to every statement. Out of the 30 statements, 4 statements have been deleted by Goodness of Fit Test, and the remaining 26 items are retained. So, the second draft of the tool comprised 26 items excluding the following the four items from the first draft.

S.No	Statements Deleted
1	I hold membership in certain interest clubs. (D1)
2	I put up good teacher behaviour before my students. (D2)
3	My classroom instructions help students understand their importance, relevance and application to real life. (D2)
4	My students are capable of differentiating their friends of true trustworthiness from the fake ones. (D3)

Note: () indicates the dimensions of the draft tool

Construct Validity:

Using the tabulated data, after the deletion of four items, the item- dimension total correlation was computed for each statement to establish the construct validity of the tool. Table 3 reveals the item-total correlation for all the 26 items.

Table 3: Item- Total correlation value for Items of the Teachers’ Social Capital Scale

S.No	r value	Remark	S.No	r value	Remark
1	0.48	Retained	14	0.52	Retained
2	0.51	Retained	15	0.61	Retained
3	0.56	Retained	16	0.47	Retained
4	0.50	Retained	17	0.39	Retained
5	0.49	Retained	18	0.51	Retained
6	0.62	Retained	19	0.48	Retained
7	0.47	Retained	20	0.42	Retained
8	0.64	Retained	21	0.53	Retained
9	0.14*	Deleted	22	0.58	Retained
10	0.58	Retained	23	0.62	Retained
11	0.51	Retained	24	0.48	Retained
12	0.64	Retained	25	0.55	Retained
13	0.59	Retained	26	0.11*	Deleted

Note: Significant value is 0.196 at 5% level & 0.256 at 1% level

* Item deleted

From the Table 3, it may be seen that 24 statements are significantly correlated with their respective dimensions, hence retained in the tool; whereas the two statements not securing significant correlation with their dimensions were deleted as mentioned below.

S.No	Statements Deleted
1	I feel, I am regarded in the local community as an expert in education. (D1)
2	I am happy that my students have started practicing their obligation to family, school and to the community. (D3)

Note: () indicates the dimensions of the draft tool

Thereafter, dimension total-total composite score correlation was computed and the results of the computation are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Dimension Total - Total Composite Score Correlation of Teachers’ Social Capital Scale

S.No.	Dimensions	‘r’ value	Significance
1	Social Structure	0.74	0.00
2	Shared Understandings	0.72	0.00
3	Nature and Quality of Relationships	0.79	0.00

Since the correlation between dimensions and total score of Teachers’ Social Capital Scale is significant at 1% level, the contribution of dimensions to the total score is confirmed and all the dimensions are retained in the draft tool.

Factorial Validity:

Finally the researcher has decided to make the process of validation complete by using factor analysis. The partially validated draft tool was again administered to another group of 100 teachers chosen by random from different category of schools in and around Chennai to complete the process of factor analysis. The process of factor analysis started with the extraction of communality values for all the 24 items as furnished in Table 5.

Table 5: Extracted Communality Value of Teachers’ Social Capital Scale

Item No	Initial	Extraction	Item No	Initial	Extraction	Item No	Initial	Extraction
1	1	0.73	9	1	0.72	17	1	0.79
2	1	0.78	10	1	0.74	18	1	0.84
3	1	0.81	11	1	0.78	19	1	0.77
4	1	0.80	12	1	0.76	20	1	0.82
5	1	0.71	13	1	0.69	21	1	0.76
6	1	0.72	14	1	0.79	22	1	0.75
7	1	0.79	15	1	0.71	23	1	0.75
8	1	0.74	16	1	0.74	24	1	0.69

It may be observed from Table 5 that all the 24 items have recorded more than 0.69, proving their suitability for inclusion in the tool.

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis

Following the computation of total variance, the initial Eigen values leading to extraction of sums of squared loadings was done and the results are furnished in Table 6.

Table 6: Total variance explained-Eigen values-extraction of squared loadings for Teachers' Social Capital Scale

Component	Initial Eigen values			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.967	20.694	20.694	4.967	20.694	20.694
2	3.085	12.853	33.548	3.085	12.853	33.548
3	1.766	7.357	40.905	1.766	7.357	40.905
4	1.725	7.188	48.093	1.725	7.188	48.093
5	1.635	6.812	54.905	1.635	6.812	54.905
6	1.484	6.182	61.087	1.484	6.182	61.087
7	1.293	5.388	66.475			
8	1.006	4.193	70.668			
9	.912	3.800	74.467			
10	.860	3.585	78.052			
11	.737	3.069	81.121			
12	.672	2.799	83.920			
13	.669	2.789	86.708			
14	.557	2.322	89.030			
15	.495	2.062	91.092			
16	.391	1.631	92.723			
17	.333	1.390	94.112			
18	.283	1.181	95.293			
19	.263	1.096	96.389			
20	.242	1.008	97.397			
21	.219	.913	98.310			
22	.164	.685	98.996			
23	.143	.594	99.589			
24	.099	.411	100.000			

From Table 6, it may be understood that the three components have secured initial Eigen values explaining 7.35% to 20.69% of variance. Moreover, the sums of extracted squared loadings reveal that the first three components account for 40.91% of the composite score value.

The sums of squared values computed by varimax rotation reveal that the first three components are distinct, scoring 7.35 and above, whereas the components four onwards are not distinctly independent as they have scored less than 7.35. Further, all the three components, subjected to the principal component analysis with rotation method of Kaiser Normalization to have yielded loadings for all the 24 items. Table 7 provides the rotated component matrix.

Table 7: Principal Component Analysis values of Teachers' Social Capital Scale

Items	Components		
	1	2	3
Item 1	.636	.248	.245
Item 2	.416	-.320	-.439
Item 3	.274	.051	.600
Item 4	.309	.539	-.353
Item 5	.408	-.057	.549
Item 6	.644	.245	.103
Item 7	.270	.513	-.086
Item 8	.563	-.412	.395
Item 9	.449	-.595	.602
Item 10	.614	-.263	.017
Item 11	.309	.601	-.451
Item 12	.485	-.168	.501
Item 13	.605	.102	.042
Item 14	.430	.548	.330
Item 15	.556	.005	.637
Item 16	-.090	.513	.395
Item 17	.621	-.068	.072
Item 18	.558	-.320	.570

Item 19	.011	.576	.374
Item 20	.239	-.445	.539
Item 21	.551	.560	-.099
Item 22	.594	.088	-.345
Item 23	.381	-.172	.540
Item 24	.066	.582	-.035

Table 7 furnishes the factor loadings of the items of the Teachers' Social Capital Scale under different dimensions selected. Then the items having significant factor loadings are grouped according to the magnitude of factor loadings. Table 8 gives the organization of the statements under different components.

Table 8: Item Distribution under 3 dimensions of Teachers' Social Capital Scale

S.No	Components		
	1	2	3
1	1	4	3
2	2	7	5
3	6	11	9
4	8	14	12
5	10	16	15
6	13	19	18
7	17	21	20
8	22	24	23

Pilot Study II:

Reliability:

The reliability coefficient of the tool has been established by Cronbach's Alpha method. The computed reliability coefficient 0.84 shows that the tool is highly reliable. Thereafter to verify the internal consistency of the prepared instrument the Cronbach's Alpha test was extended to yield alpha value for each of the 24 items by excluding the contribution of each individual item on the total composite score of the tool. The results of computation are given in Table 9.

Table 9: Cronbach's Alpha value of items of Teachers' Social Capital Scale

S.No	Corrected Item Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if item deleted	S.No	Corrected Item Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if item deleted
1	0.74	0.76	13	0.73	0.81
2	0.72	0.80	14	0.80	0.79
3	0.79	0.81	15	0.81	0.72
4	0.74	0.74	16	0.74	0.80
5	0.76	0.80	17	0.73	0.84
6	0.73	0.83	18	0.70	0.81
7	0.80	0.79	19	0.80	0.79
8	0.82	0.78	20	0.80	0.80
9	0.79	0.81	21	0.84	0.79
10	0.72	0.78	22	0.79	0.78
11	0.79	0.80	23	0.78	0.80
12	0.73	0.81	24	0.80	0.79

The computed values of Cronbach's Alpha ensure the internal consistency of the instrument.

Final Form of the Tool:

Table 10: Teachers' Social Capital Scale

Instruction: Kindly go through each statement carefully, and mark your preferred response by tick (✓) mark under any one of the following scale points - Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree.

S.No	Statements	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1	I have close ties with teachers of different departments of our institution.					
2	I know the implications of the code of conduct of teachers.					
3	I trust the goodness of my students to reciprocate my sincerity.					
4	I am familiar with teachers of other institutions in our locality.					

5	I am careful about my language while interacting with my students.					
6	I am a person of worth to all those who are in contact with me.					
7	I am a member of an academic oriented / social community related organization.					
8	My directions to students are short, progressive and to the point.					
9	The parents of my students acknowledge my trustworthiness.					
10	I take part in subject oriented associations functioning in different institutions.					
11	While narrating, I restrict myself to avoid unrelated and lengthy explanations.					
12	I introduce my students to emulate the spirit of living for others.					
13	I am aware of different roles a teacher has to play inside and outside of the class.					
14	I am conscious of the problems arising in the class due to the negative attitudes of a few.					
15	My students are hesitant to mock at others, as it degrades their dignity.					
16	My past students are in good positions in the society.					
17	I appreciate the beliefs of my students; however I let them understand what my beliefs are.					
18	My students, don't exhibit any odd or affected behaviour.					
19	I strictly follow the school procedure in executing my planned activities.					
20	I believe in the goodness of pleasing words and expressions to calm down the turbulent hearts of students.					
21	I make it a point to make at least one past student to interact with the students of my class.					
22	I am an active member of the local health/fitness club.					
23	I uphold the moral values as the primary ones in the life of students.					
24	I help the students of my class to develop certain unique characteristics that differentiate them from others.					

The items meant for different dimensions of the Final Form of the Tool are furnished in Table 11.

Table 11: Items of the Teachers' Social Capital Scale – Dimension wise

Dimensions	Statements
Social Structure	1, 4, 7, 10, 13, 16, 19, 22
Shared Understandings	2, 5, 8, 11, 14, 17, 20, 23
Nature and Quality of Relationships	3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 21, 24

Scoring Scheme:

The 24 items of the scale are in statement form. For each item, the respondent is to indicate his/her preference by putting tick (✓) mark under the 5 point scale - Strongly Agree, Agree, Undecided, Disagree, Strongly Disagree. Since all the statements are positive in nature, each item carries score 5 for Strongly agree, 4 for Agree, 3 for Undecided, 2 for Disagree, and 1 for Strongly disagree. Thereby, one can score the minimum of 24 and maximum of 120 by responding to all the items.

Grade Norm:

Drawing a sample of 1250 teachers of different cadres from different categories of schools from the five regions of Tamilnadu – East, West, Central, North and South – Teachers' Social Capital Scale was administered. A bell shaped normal curve emerged on plotting scores of the tool without statistically significant skewness. As such by employing M+/- 1 S.D, the nature of Social Capital was decided and marked as High – Moderate - Low.

Nature of Social Capital	Score Range
High	Above 90
Moderate	52 - 89
Low	51 and Below

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